

ASAP CRN Cloud Release

Major Release DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20186059](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20186059)

README - Release [v5.0.0](#)

Overview

The ASAP CRN Cloud is pleased to announce the 5.0.0 release of data which expands to include two new Curated Collections, with the curation of three previously released Datasets. We are introducing the **PMDBS scATACseq Collection** of Datasets, and the **Invitro Bulk RNAseq Collection**. Additionally, as with all Major CRN Cloud Releases, all dataset metadata has been formatted to be up to date with our most recent Common Data Elements (CDE), v4.4.

New Collections

- **PMDBS scATACseq Collection, v1.0.0** - DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20400469](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20400469)
- **Invitro Bulk RNAseq Collection, v1.0.0** - DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20400939](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20400939)

Updated Collections

- **PMDBS scRNAseq Collection, v3.1.2** - DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20403941](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20403941)
- **PMDBS Bulk RNAseq Collection, v1.2.2** - DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20403867](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20403867)
- **PMDBS Spatial RNAseq Collection, v1.1.2** - DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20403929](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20403929)
- **Mouse Spatial RNAseq Collection, v1.0.1** - DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20403845](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20403845)
- **Mouse scRNAseq Collection, v1.0.1** - DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20403854](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20403854)

ASAP Teams: See [CRN Cloud Authorship List](#) for the full list of contributing investigators/researchers by dataset.

ASAP CRN GitHub: github.com/ASAP-CRN

Data Release Date: 2026-06-15

ASAP CRN Cloud Release Number: v5.0.0

ASAP CRN Release DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.8384742](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8384742)

Curated Data File Manifest: [ASAP CRN Cloud File Manifest - v3.1](#)

New / Updated Datasets

PMDBS scATACseq

Datasets curated with the pmdbs_atac_rnaseq workflow:

- o voet-pmdbs-sn-atacseq-10x, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18988729](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18988729)

In-Vitro Bulk RNAseq

Datasets curated with the invitro_bulk_rnaseq workflow:

- o jakobsson-invivo-bulk-rnaseq-dopaminergic, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17149266](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17149266) (previously released)
- o jakobsson-invivo-bulk-rnaseq-microglia, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17149290](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17149290) (previously released)
- o cohort-invivo-bulk-rnaseq, DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20400939](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20400939) (collection version doi)

Collection Details

Collection Version Updates (cohort Datasets)

[PMDBS scRNAseq Collection](#), v3.1.1 -> v3.1.2

- cohort-pmdbs-sc-rnaseq , DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20403941](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20403941) (collection version doi)

[PMDBS Bulk RNAseq Collection](#), -> v1.2.1 -> v1.2.2

- cohort-pmdbs-bulk-rnaseq , DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20403867](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20403867) (collection version doi)

[PMDBS Spatial RNAseq Collection](#), v1.1.1 -> v1.1.2

[Mouse Spatial RNAseq Collection](#), v1.0.0 -> v1.0.1

[Mouse scRNAseq Collection](#), v1.0.0 -> v1.0.1

- cohort-mouse-sc-rnaseq , DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20403854](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20403854) (collection version doi)

New Collections

[PMDBS scATACseq Collection](#), v1.0.0

Workflow Release - v1.0.0

- GitHub release [link](#)

[Invitro Bulk RNAseq Collection](#), v1.0.0

Workflow Release - v2.0.0

- GitHub release [link](#)

Raw Data

The *raw* data refers to the fastq files transferred by each ASAP CRN Team. These data are available with the caveat that they are stored in “requester pays” buckets on the google cloud platform. A google cloud billing account will need to be registered to access these data. More information is available [HERE](#). gs://asap-raw-[<team_name>](#)-[<source>](#)-[<dataset_name>](#)

Metadata & Data Dictionary

The ASAP CRN Common Data Elements ([CDE](#)) outlines the variables which are harmonized across the ASAP CRN. These metadata enable the harmonization of the data submitted by multiple teams. The metadata consists of five tables, which are described below.

Metadata refers to descriptive information about the overall study, individual samples, all protocols, and references to processed and raw data file names. Metadata was aggregated using the table-based submission for each team's dataset. The tables - **STUDY**, **PROTOCOL**, **SUBJECT**, **SAMPLE**, **DATA**, etc. - can be thought of as spreadsheets, and each table is prepared as simple .csv files which constitute the tables outlined in the [ASAP CRN CDE](#). These have been aggregated across submissions and unique ASAP IDs generated for each dataset, team, subject and sample. I.e. ASAP_dataset_id, ASAP_team_id, ASAP_subject_id, and ASAP_sample_id.

The metadata can be browsed on [ASAP CRN Cloud Explorer](#) and exposed in [Verily Workbench](#).

[This document](#).